

Assessment of School Heads' Management Practices on Teachers' Professional Development

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ABSTRACT

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Teachers' professional development is crucial for fostering a high-quality educational environment. It equips teachers with the latest pedagogical skills, enhances their knowledge base, and ensures they remain effective in delivering curriculum content. School heads' management practices for teachers' professional development are vital for significantly enhancing educational quality and outcomes. Mentoring, facilitating training attendance, and making strategic teacher assignments are all effective management practices that can foster a supportive and growth-oriented environment. This study aimed to assess the school heads' management practices on the professional development of elementary teachers. The study utilized a descriptive survey method, collecting data from 21 school heads and 186 teachers through a validated researcher-made questionnaire and unstructured interviews. Statistical analysis, including a weighted mean and an independent t-test, was employed to interpret the data. The study revealed that school heads view their management practices in mentoring, training attendance, and teacher assignments as highly effective, whereas they perceive monitoring as moderately effective. However, teachers generally rated these practices as moderately effective, highlighting a discrepancy between the two groups' perceptions. Significant differences were noted in their perceptions of mentoring, training attendance, and assignments; however, both groups are aligned in their perceptions of the effectiveness of monitoring practices as moderately effective.

KEYWORDS:

administrative practices, instructional practices, teachers management practices, professional development

1. INTRODUCTION

Over the years, the educational system has continued to change to cope with the needs of the new generation of learners. This rapid growth has led to numerous management issues within the education system, which require resolution. To solve the problem, there is a need to reshape, re-direct, and re-orient the systems so that they can respond to the challenges of the 21st century. Educators, especially school heads and teachers, need to update themselves personally and professionally through training, workshops, and the pursuit of graduate studies to keep pace with the rapid change in the educational system.

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Teachers' professional growth and learning must be given more attention. This is one way of supporting teachers with the increasingly complex skills students need to learn in preparation for further education and work in the 21st century. To develop pupils' competencies such as deep mastery of challenging content, critical thinking, complex problem-solving, effective communication and collaboration, and self-direction, we need sophisticated and innovative forms of teaching. In turn, effective professional development is needed to help teachers learn and refine the pedagogy required to teach these skills. The school leaders' participation has a great impact on the growth and development of teachers (Hilton et al., 2015).

Currently, educators perceive the need for professional development as a requirement to meet standards to enhance instruction and learning. According to Ingvarson et al. (2005), the goal of professional development for teachers is to equip them with the knowledge and abilities

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needed to support students' education by conducting investigations that focus on scientific inquiry techniques they have already taught. However, teacher trainers are now seen as professionals, and their continuing professional development is unavoidably increasing. Moreover, teacher educators should be dynamic mediators in their growth by keeping themselves updated with new information, developing, and improving knowledge on education and teacher instruction to enhance and boost their teaching. (Nabhani et al., 2017).

The school heads have a significant influence on the teachers' professional development. Furthermore, the professional development of teachers is essential to educational reform, as we are continuously facing the next generation of learners. It is vital to assert that it is critically important in developing and enriching learners' academic and life-long skills (Mthani & Msiza, 2023). According to Cerna (2014), the school head has a vital impact on the learners' and teachers' performance in the school system. The support for teachers at the school level significantly influences the success of their professional development programs. While recognizing the importance of various stakeholders in teacher professional development, it is essential for schools and the Department of Education to allocate adequate financial and human resources. The professional development of elementary teachers is vital for effective teaching and learning, as they are responsible for providing basic education. This development involves learning opportunities that enable teachers to adapt to changes in the education system, ultimately enhancing their effectiveness (Smith & Gillespie, 2007).

In the Philippines, DepEd Memorandum No. 50 s. 2020 emphasizes the importance of professional development for teachers and school leaders. This memorandum prioritizes professional development to support the continuous upskilling and reskilling of educators, aligning with the department's goal of improving learning outcomes. The launching of the MATATAG program to address challenges in delivering quality education to Filipino schoolchildren highlights the need for teachers professional development. The MATATAG program, titled "*Bansang Makabata, Batang Makabansa*," embodies critical components aimed at enhancing the education system. One of the program's priorities is to support teachers in their professional development, which aligns with the Department of Education's commitment to valuing the welfare of teachers as much as it values the learners.

Previous studies have predominantly focused on the correlation between school heads' educational management practices and students' outcomes, leaving limited research on the impact of these practices on teachers' professional development. To address this gap, this study aimed to assess

the management practices of school heads in Sorsogon West District, Sorsogon City, regarding elementary teachers' professional development for the school year 2023-2024. Specifically, the study set out to address the following sub-problems: (1) What is the extent of management practices employed by school heads on elementary teachers' professional development as perceived by the school heads themselves along: (a) mentoring teachers, (b) teachers' attendance at training, (c) teachers' assignments; and (d) monitoring of teachers. (2) What is the extent of the management practices employed by school heads on elementary teachers' professional development as perceived by the teachers along the identified variables? (3) Is there a significant difference between the perceptions of the respondents and the management practices of the school heads along the identified variables?

II. METHODOLOGY

The descriptive-survey method was used to determine the extent of effectiveness of the management practices of the school heads on the professional development of the elementary teachers in Sorsogon West District, Sorsogon City Division, for the school year 2023-2024. The extent of effectiveness of the management practices of school heads, along with mentoring of teachers, teachers' training, teachers' assignments, and monitoring of teachers, was measured.

The Respondents

The respondents of the study were the 21 total enumeration of public school heads, and 186 elementary teachers from the three hundred sixty-one elementary teachers, which represent 52% of the total number of teachers in the Sorsogon West District, Sorsogon City Division. Moreover, school heads demographic profile were also asked during the unstructured interview. The teacher respondents were selected through purposive random sampling using the Slovin formula with a standard error of 5% or 0.05. This formula was used to determine the number of samples from the teachers' population.

Data Collection Materials and Procedures

A researcher-made survey questionnaire was used to gather the needed research data. The same set of questionnaires was used for both school heads and teachers. The instrument used by the researcher was a quality-assured non-test research instrument in the form of a researcher-made survey questionnaire to determine the management practices of the school heads on the professional development of the elementary teachers in Sorsogon West. The researcher conducted a dry run to test the validity and reliability of the instrument. There were seven school heads and 10 elementary teachers from the Division of Sorsogon province that participated in the dry run. The results were tested through the Cronbach reliability test, and the interpretation was found to be acceptable. Cronbach's alpha coefficients were generated

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(Bolorinwa, 2016; Trizano-Hermosilla & Alvarado, 2016) to assess the internal consistency of the survey questionnaire. The overall result of Cronbach's alpha coefficient was 0.97, with excellent internal consistency. This result indicates that the instrument was highly reliable, it produces consistent and dependable results. The researcher then solicited comments and suggestions from the panel members, statistician, and adviser before proceeding to the final distribution of the instruments. Upon retrieval of the survey questionnaire, the researcher conducted an unstructured interview among the school heads and teachers to validate their responses. Prior to the interview, interviewees signed a consent form. The researcher has taken notes on the responses given by the school heads and teachers. Respondents were asked in their local dialects to ensure better understanding, clearer communication, and more accurate responses. Through this approach, it fostered a comfortable and familiar environment and contributed to more genuine and insightful responses.

Data Analysis

The weighted mean was used to determine the effectiveness of the management practices of the school heads on teachers' professional development. The independent t-test was used to determine the significant difference between the perceptions of the school heads and teachers along with their management practices on teachers' professional development. The 5-point effectiveness scale below was used for the interpretation of the level of effectiveness of management practices of school heads adopted from the studies of Haramain (2019):

5	4.21 - 5.00	Very Effective
4	3.21 - 4.20	Moderately Effective
3	2.61 - 3.20	Slightly Effective
2	1.81 - 2.60	Least Effective
1	1.00 - 1.80	Not Effective

III. RESULTS

The data was grouped as follows: 1. The extent of management practices employed by school heads on elementary teachers' professional development as perceived by the school heads themselves; mentoring teachers, teachers' attendance to training, teachers' assignments, and monitoring teachers; 2. The extent of management practices employed by school heads on elementary teachers' professional development as perceived by teachers' along; the identified variables 3. The significant difference between the perceptions of the respondents on the management practices of the school heads along the identified variables; and The study's findings led to the introduction of the proposed project plan.

Extent of Management Practices Employed by School Heads on Elementary Teachers' Professional Development as Perceived by School Heads

Mentoring of Teachers

Along with the mentoring of teachers, school heads perceived that they were very effective in conducting instructional supervision using appropriate tools and strategies, providing constructive feedback and support to teachers to enhance their teaching skills, conducting instructional supervision using appropriate tools and strategies, and lastly, providing constructive feedback and support to teachers to enhance their teaching skills. These indicators had average weighted means ranging from 3.57 to 3.67, which were interpreted as very effective. This showed that school heads provided the technical assistance needed by the teachers. While the indicator with the least weighted mean was meeting the teachers one by one, the average weighted mean of 3.48 was interpreted as moderately effective.

Teachers' Attendance to Training

The school heads were very effective in encouraging teachers to participate in divisional, regional, and national seminars, courses, and training, with a weighted mean of 3.71. The lowest indicator, along with teachers' attendance, was informing teachers about the innovations in education and using resources for the innovations, with a 3.41 weighted mean. According to the school head at Sorsogon West, the school is unable to provide electronic devices for teachers due to the limited MOOE budget, which also includes teaching materials. The Department of Education provides limited teaching materials, such as laptops, televisions, internet connections, and other supplies that are beneficial to the teaching and learning process of the pupils.

Assigning Teachers' Workload

On assigning teachers workload, the highest indicator was 6. "Encourages the teachers to train and coach potential pupils in academics, sports, or any skill-based contests" with a 3.71 computed mean and very effective verbal interpretation. School heads gave teachers a chance to show their talents and skills through coaching in academic, sports, and skill-based contests. Likewise, school heads believed that they were very effective in assigning teachers to a specific assignment. The total weighted mean score of 3.64 obtained by school leaders suggests that they view their assignments to teachers as "very effective". Regarding the assignment of teachers' workload, the respondents felt that the practices were very effective. This high rating indicates that school leaders were successful in distributing workloads in a way that supports teachers' professional growth and ensures a balanced and manageable workload, contributing positively to their overall job satisfaction and performance.

Monitoring of teachers

In monitoring teachers, the following management practices have a 3.45 weighted mean: monitoring the teachers' professional needs and mental and physical well-being; conducting quarterly one-on-one meetings with the

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teachers to discuss their professional goals and progress; and conducting the quarterly classroom observation of teachers to assess the teaching-learning process of teachers. The overall perception of school heads on their management practices, along with mentoring teachers, teachers' attendance to training, assigning teachers' workload, and monitoring teachers, was 3.58, interpreted as very effective. This implied that, along with these variables, school heads were very effective in their functions as mentors, administrators, and monitoring personnel in the school.

Extent of Management Practices Employed by School Heads on Elementary Teachers' Professional Development as Perceived by Teachers

Mentoring of Teachers

Management practices that encourage collaborative learning and peer mentoring among teachers have the highest average weighted mean of 3.49, indicating that they are more effective. Conversely, the provision of technical support for teaching and learning, which could enhance teaching strategies, received the lowest average mean of 3.35, indicating moderate effectiveness. School heads were moderately effective in providing constructive feedback and support to teachers to enhance their teaching skills, offering guidance and resources to teachers to improve their constructional practices, and encouraging collaborative learning and peer mentoring among teachers. Teachers in Sorsogon West perceived the school heads as more effective in providing the technical assistance they needed. Teachers perceived the mentoring of teachers as moderately effective, with an average weighted mean score of 3.45. This implies that educational administrators in the Sorsogon West district place a significant emphasis on mentoring initiatives and actively participate in them to foster the growth and expertise of educators.

Teachers' Attendance to Training

The school heads always informed teachers on the importance of attending seminars, training, and workshops within the district and division and encouraged teachers to attend trainings and seminars and pursue higher education. These indicators gained an average weighted mean of 3.60, 3.54, and 3.54, which were interpreted as very effective.

According to teachers, school heads were very effective in encouraging them to attend seminars and pursue post-graduate studies. But despite these encouragements, teachers were not able to attend training and seminars at higher levels or even pursue post-education because of the budget deficit. Most of the teachers' salaries were just enough for their monthly consumption. They suggested that the Sorsogon City Division may have a lot of funds that teachers can lend for their post-graduate studies and training outside the division.

Assigning Teachers' Workload

The following practices, along with teachers' assignments, such as assessing the strengths and weaknesses of the teachers to make appropriate assignments, encouraging the teachers to train and coach potential pupils in academics, sports, or any skilled-based contests, assigning teachers and other personnel in the area of their competence and expertise, and ensuring equitable distribution of assignments to give teachers opportunities for diverse experiences, have the average weighted means of 3.46, 3.34, 3.36, and 3.43, respectively, interpreted as moderately effective.

Teachers believed that they were moderately effective in the above-mentioned practices, but very effective in providing support and resources to teachers for the successful completion of their tasks, with a weighted mean of 3.51. This suggests that while teachers acknowledge their proficiency in various professional duties, the additional support and resources provided by school leaders significantly enhance their ability to perform tasks effectively. The overall computed average weighted mean score of 3.43 obtained by school leaders as perceived by teachers was moderately effective.

Monitoring Teachers

Along with the monitoring of teachers, school heads were moderately effective, as perceived by teachers. Generally, they were moderately effective in the following practices: conducting quarterly one-on-one meetings with the teachers to discuss their professional goals and progress; conducting the quarterly classroom observation of teachers to assess the teaching-learning process of teachers; conducting the mid-year Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF) evaluation as scheduled; and implementing a system for peer evaluation and feedback among teachers with the average weighted means of 3.41., 3.42, 3.32, and 3.35. According to teachers, because of the broad scope of school heads' functions and responsibilities, monitoring every teacher was not done regularly. The overall teacher's perception has an average weighted mean of 3.41, with a verbal interpretation of moderately effective. This implies that teachers believed school heads performed their functions more effectively but acknowledged room for improvement, particularly in monitoring.

Difference between the Perceptions of Teachers and School Heads on the latter's Management Practices on Teachers Professional Development

As shown in Table 5, the t-computed value of 4.84 is greater than the t-critical value of 2.23 at the 0.05 level of significance when the degree of freedom is 12. This indicates the rejection of the null hypothesis and a significant difference in the perceptions of the two groups of respondents regarding the effectiveness of mentoring teachers. Likewise, the t-computed value of 2.30 under teachers' attendance at

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training is within the t-critical value of 2.18 at a 0.05 level of significance when the degree of freedom is 12. This implies that we can reject the null hypothesis of no significant difference. Along with the with the teachers' assignment, the computed t-value of 6.48 is greater than the t-critical value of 2.18 at a 0.05 level of significance when the degree of freedom is 12. Therefore, we can reject the null hypothesis. Along with the monitoring of teachers, the computed t-value of 0.69 is within the t-critical value of 2.18 at a 0.05 level of significance when the degree of freedom is 12. Therefore, we cannot reject the null hypothesis. This means that there is no significant difference between the perceptions of the two groups of respondents in terms of effectiveness in monitoring teachers.

Table 1. Statistical Analyses

Statistical Bases	Statistical Analyses			
	A	B	C	D
Level of Significance	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05
Degree of freedom	12	12	12	12
t critical value	2.23	2.18	2.18	2.18
t computed value	-4.84	-2.30	-6.48	-0.69
Decision on Ho	Reject	Reject	Reject	Do not reject
Conclusion	Sig	Sig	Sig	Not Sig

Legend: A-Mentoring of Teachers, B-Teachers' Attendance to Trainings, C-Assigning Teachers Workload, D-Monitoring of Teachers

IV. DISCUSSION

School heads perceived that they were very effective in conducting instructional supervision using appropriate tools, providing constructive feedback and supporting teachers to enhance their teaching skills, offering guidance and resources to teachers to improve their instructional practices, and providing technical support on the teaching-learning process that could help to improve the strategies of teachers in delivering their lessons. The following indicators have average weighted means of 3.67, 3.67, 3.57, and 3.62 consecutively, with verbal interpretations of "very effective".

In the study of du Plessis (2018), on the roles of the school head department in the professional development of teachers, they found out that they have the direct responsibilities and accountabilities that greatly affect the development of educators. The school principals provide mentorship and guidance to teachers for their professional growth. The school heads provide instructional supervision

using appropriate tools and strategies. During the classroom observation, the school heads immediately mentor the teachers through the post-conference phase, as indicated in DepEd Memorandum No. 008, S. 2023 and DepEd Order No. 42, S. 2017.

On teachers' attendance at training, school heads are very effective as perceived by themselves. They effectively encouraged teachers to participate in training, seminars, and workshops that complemented their professional development. The school heads in the Sorsogon West district were very effective in encouraging teachers to pursue higher education and attend seminars, workshops, and training that were beneficial for their professional and personal growth, with the computed weighted mean of 3.71 interpreted as very effective. Subsequently, they identified pertinent training, programs, and workshops that complemented teachers' professional development, conveyed to them the significance of these trainings for their professional advancement, and motivated teachers to pursue higher education, all of which yielded a computed mean of 3.67, which was considered highly effective.

The weighted mean scores along this indicator were 3.61, suggesting that school heads view teachers' attendance at training as "very effective". The high weighted mean score indicates strong support from school heads for teachers' attendance at training sessions, reflecting a proactive approach to professional development that is likely to yield positive outcomes for both teachers and students.

This shows that school heads value and promote teachers' involvement in professional development opportunities to advance their expertise. According to Darling-Hammond and McLaughlin (1995), to provide pupils with a high-quality education, educators should continuously improve themselves on a professional level. Heads of schools advise their staff members about seminars and training programs that support teachers' professional, mental, physical, and emotional growth. The knowledge gained from participation in training and seminars was beneficial for the continuous development of teachers; these also helped in elevating the pupils' performance. Furthermore, pursuing postgraduate education provides deeper knowledge and new pedagogical strategies, which can improve classroom instruction and student outcomes. Continuing education helps teachers stay updated with the latest educational research, teaching methods, and technology.

Along with the teachers' assignments, school heads were very effective in assigning teachers and personnel in the area of their competence, knowledge, skills, and expertise. Based on the data gathered, school heads assign teachers and other personnel in the area of their expertise, assign teachers as coordinators based on the training and seminars they attended, and endorse appointments and promotions based on

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the merit of teachers. These management practices have the same computed weighted means of 3.67, which is interpreted as very effective. Encouraging teachers to train and coach potential pupils in academics, sports, or any skill-based contest has the highest average weighted mean of 3.71, interpreted as very effective. The overall weighted mean score for teachers' assignments was 3.64, which was interpreted as very effective.

In addition to their 6-hour actual teaching load and their 2-hour preparation of instructional materials, teachers were required to carry out other ancillary duties as per DepEd Order No. 12. They performed unstructured interviews and teacher profiling to determine the appropriate supplementary function to assign to instructors before providing them with tasks and coordinators. This suggests that to improve teachers' effectiveness, school leaders should allocate coordinators and assign tasks that are in line with their areas of experience and skill. By aligning these additional responsibilities with teachers' strengths, school leaders can ensure more efficient task execution and promote a more collaborative and supportive work environment, ultimately leading to improved educational outcomes.

On the monitoring of teachers, the management practices have the same weighted mean of 3.43, interpreted as more effective; monitor teachers' professional needs and mental and physical well-being, conduct quarterly one-on-one meetings with teachers to discuss their professional goals and progress, conduct quarterly classroom evaluations of teachers, and implement a system for peer evaluation and feedback. The management practice with the lowest weighted mean was conducting the midyear Individual Performance Commitment and Review (IPCRF) as scheduled with a 3.44 with a verbal interpretation of more effective.

During the unstructured interview, the school heads stated that the complexity of managing, directing, and overseeing the entire school and its personnel led to the addition of ancillary tasks, which they began last school year. They cannot conduct the monitoring at the scheduled time. This statement was strengthened with the release of DepEd Order No. 002, S. 2024, which emphasized the immediate removal of the administrative loads for teachers. If the school has an administrative officer, they will receive additional workloads, or the school heads will take on all these responsibilities. The school heads received the coordinatorships, including Disaster Risk Reduction Management, Gender and Development, and other ancillary tasks unrelated to teaching and learning. The power, duty, and accountability to oversee the school rest with the school heads, as specified by Republic Act No. 9155. They are responsible for managing projects and programs. As a result, the extensive range of duties also includes administrative duties. Despite their continued success, the score suggests

that school leaders could enhance their monitoring strategies. School heads' monitoring practices gained the lowest computed mean for both teachers' and school heads' perceptions, which has an average computed mean of 3.42. These findings implied that school heads should focus on monitoring teachers quarterly, as suggested under DepEd Order 42, s. 2017, and DepEd Memo No. 4, s. 2022.

The Extent of Management Practices Employed by School Heads on Elementary Teachers' Professional Development as perceived by the Teachers

The average weighted mean score for the mentoring of teachers by teachers was 3.61, which was regarded as very effective. This implies that educational administrators in the Sorsogon West district place a significant emphasis on mentoring initiatives and actively participate in them as a means to foster the growth and expertise of educators. The school heads provide instructional supervision using appropriate tools and strategies.

This implies that educational administrators in the Sorsogon West district place a significant emphasis on mentoring initiatives and actively participate in them to foster the growth and expertise of educators. In the study of Lebitania (2022), mentoring teachers has a significant impact on their professional development. School heads were very effective in providing instructional supervision using appropriate tools, constructive feedback, and support, they encouraged collaborative learning and peer mentoring among teachers. Peer mentoring greatly helped teachers' professional and personal development. Through peer mentoring, they develop mutual growth, build networks, and feel empowered as they can easily relate to and share their experiences with their peers. The handbook on instructional coaching and mentoring developed by Palacio & Digo (2024) may help them in this particular task. According to the study by Ali et al. (2018), school head mentoring and coaching greatly affect the professional development of teachers as well as administrators. To achieve a successful mentoring and coaching there should be a continuous learning, clear roles, time and a friendly-learning environment.

The weighted mean scores along this indicator were 3.61, suggesting that school heads view teachers' attendance at training as very effective. This suggests that school heads involve teachers in professional development opportunities, training, seminars, and any form of career advancement to enhance their expertise. These developments were essential to providing pupils with a high-quality education. Educators should continuously improve themselves on a professional level.

School heads value and promote teachers' involvement in professional development opportunities to advance their expertise, these findings were similar to the findings in the study of Mancenille (2020). She emphasized

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the importance of attending training, seminars, and other forms of career advancement among teachers. These were essentials for improving and elevating the performance of the learners and the school.

Fatih (2020) supported this by stating that teachers' attendance at seminars and trainings is an indispensable component of their professional development within the education sector. These events offer educators invaluable opportunities for growth, allowing them to expand their knowledge, refine their skills, and stay abreast of the latest advancements in teaching methodologies and educational technologies. Teachers not only enhance their own pedagogical practices by participating in seminars and trainings, but they also contribute to the overall improvement of the education system. Additionally, the collaborative nature of these events cultivates a sense of community among educators, allowing them to exchange best practices and innovative ideas to enhance their students' learning experiences Ahmad et al. (2021)

In addition to assigning teachers, the most effective practices, with a weighted mean of 3.51, involved providing necessary support and resources to teachers to ensure their successful completion of assigned tasks. The practice of assigning teachers and other personnel in their areas of competence and expertise, as well as designating teachers as coordinators based on their attendance at seminars and training, yielded the lowest weighted mean of 3.34, indicating greater effectiveness.

School heads demonstrated moderate effectiveness in assigning teachers to their ancillary functions, taking into account their expertise, skills, talents, and attendance at seminars. This result was similar to the findings of Borgoños (2022) in her study on school heads' management practices and elementary teachers' performance in Calauan, Laguna. She pointed out that school heads were firm in making decisions about assigning tasks to their teachers. Furthermore, she advocated for rewarding and promoting teachers based on their achievements.

This suggests that school heads were only moderately effective in assigning teachers to their special tasks and additional workload, as perceived by the teachers. They may improve their management practices with this variable. Assigning teachers based on their skills, talents, and expertise improves student learning and the school community's academic performance. Furthermore, it fosters professional growth and development among teachers. Matching teachers with subjects they are skilled and passionate about is likely to enhance their performance and keep them updated with current trends in their field of expertise.

The management practices, which include monitoring teachers through quarterly one-on-one meetings

to discuss their professional progress, conducting quarterly classroom observations to assess the curriculum and strategies, and conducting midyear IPCRF evaluations as scheduled, have resulted in weighted means of 3.31, 3.32, and 3.32 consecutively, with verbal interpretations indicating more effectiveness. Moreover, the school heads' management practices, which focused on the professional development of teachers across the identified variables, demonstrated greater effectiveness, with an average weighted mean of 3.42. There was a significant difference between the perceptions of the teachers and school heads' on the extent of the effectiveness of their management practices, including mentoring, teachers' attendance, training, teachers' assignments, and monitoring of teachers.

Effectively, school heads have broader responsibilities in the school as mandated in Republic Act 9155, otherwise known as the Governance of Basic Education Act of 2001 and their profile as school heads have a significant effect on their functions and management practices as administrators in school (Barola and Digo, 2022). Thus, the extensive range of administrative duties may bring about unnecessary stress for both the school heads and their subordinates. Hence, stressors along with their mentoring, monitoring activities and other administrative duties may be handled along with their own coping mechanisms (Desabayla & Digo, 2023; 2024).

Difference between the Perceptions of Teachers and School Heads on the latter's Management Practices on Teachers Professional Development

The statistical analysis revealed significant differences between the perceptions of school heads and teachers regarding the effectiveness of mentoring, teachers' attendance at training, and teachers' assignments. The t-values for mentoring (4.84), and teachers' assignments (6.48) were both higher than the t-critical value of 2.18 at a 0.05 level of significance with 12 degrees of freedom. This meant that the null hypothesis was not true, and that there were significant differences in how people saw things. For teachers' attendance at training, the t-value of 2.30 was also higher than the t-critical value of 2.18. This meant that the null hypothesis was rejected and there was a significant difference in how the two groups saw things. These findings were comparable to Haramanian's (2019) study on school principals' management practices to enhance excellence. His study revealed that there was a significant difference between the perceptions of the teachers and the school principals on the extent of effectiveness of the educational management practices they employed.

V. CONCLUSION

In light of the findings of the study, it can be concluded that the extent of management practices of the school heads, along with mentoring of teachers, teachers' attendance to

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training, teachers' assignments, and monitoring of teachers, were very effective. It suggests a strong commitment from educational administrators in the Sorsogon West District to nurture educators' growth and expertise. This emphasis on mentoring initiatives underscores the proactive involvement of school leaders in supporting teachers' professional development, ultimately contributing to a more healthy educational environment. The educational administrators in the Sorsogon West district place a significant emphasis on mentoring initiatives and actively participate in them as a means to foster the growth and expertise of educators. Similarly, teachers perceived school heads' management practices, including mentoring, training, attendance, assignments, and monitoring, as moderately effective. It may suggest a potential gap in communication or understanding between school leaders and teachers. This highlights the importance of transparent communication and collaboration to align perceptions and ensure mutual understanding of professional development initiatives. Additionally, it underscores the need for school leaders to actively solicit feedback from teachers and involve them in decision-making processes to enhance the effectiveness of management practices. Finally, there was a significant difference between the perceptions of the respondents and the identified variables. School heads perceived their management practices as highly effective in enhancing teachers' professional development, whereas teachers perceived these practices to be moderately effective.

Hence, this paper suggests that a contextualized and localized professional development project may be proposed to improve the management practices of school heads and the professional development of teachers. Implementing this initiative as a structured and formal professional development plan within our school community presents an opportunity to elevate teacher professional development, collaboration, and innovation, which could improve students' performance.

VI. DISCLOSURE

We affirm that we do not have material or financial interests relevant to the research described in this paper that establish a conflict of interest.

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